

The Effect Of Using An Educational Approach By A Generative Learning Strategy In Learning The Skill Of Serving In Tennis

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 19, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: March 18, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Learning, Teaching, Tennis, Student</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4618625</p>	<p><i>Learning methods in general and physical education in particular have a share of scientific development. Various advanced methods have emerged that have been used in all fields of physical education that have been able to achieve advanced results in learning and developing skills and activities, which have been able to work on transferring some teaching decisions from a teacher control center to a student control center. Then the student himself becomes the focus of the educational process, especially if the most appropriate method is chosen. The importance of the research lies in the effect of using a generative learning strategy on teaching the skill of serving in tennis. The researcher used the experimental method for its suitability and the nature of the research, and a sample was formed from the fourth stage of middle school students for Al Mutamaizen prep school in Baghdad. And their number is (20). The researcher concluded that there has been an improvement in the level of teaching the skill of serving in tennis as a result of using the generative learning strategy.</i></p>

Introduction

Learning methods in general and physical education in particular have a share of scientific development. Various advanced methods have emerged that have been used in all fields of physical education that have been able to achieve advanced results in learning and developing skills and activities, which have been able to work on transferring some teaching decisions from a teacher control center to a student control center. Then the student himself becomes the focus of the educational process, especially if the most appropriate method is chosen. The importance of the research lies in the effect of using a **generative learning** strategy on teaching the skill of serving in tennis. The researcher used the experimental method for its suitability and the nature of the research, and a sample was formed from the fourth stage of middle school students for Al Mutamaizen prep school in Baghdad. And their number is (20). The researcher concluded that there has been an improvement in the level of teaching the skill of serving in tennis as a result of using the generative learning strategy.

1-1 Introduction and importance of research

Individual games are characterized by their different levels and the multiplicity of their practices and purposes, as the continuous interest in progress and achieving the highest levels of sports performance, whether it is using mathematical and applied sciences, or scientific methods and modern teaching methods in order to solve the problems facing the player or the learner in achieving the best technical performance or the best level.

The goal of teachers or those in charge of the educational process and leaders entrusted to those working in the field of sports is to find and use the best and most efficient methods and techniques to build the complete sports personality, and the methods and techniques of teaching physical education contribute to achieving this goal. The physical education lesson is the basic shape that the educational process progresses through and under the teacher's instructions and directives, the students' complete physical readiness, as well as strengthening the various body systems and developing physical characteristics and motor skills. The teaching process is of three dimensions, consisting of a teacher, a learner and an educational material, provided that this process leads to learning and the development of various aspects of learning (cognitive, kinesthetic, Physical and psychomotor), and there must be interaction between the teacher, the learner and the educational material

Many studies have been conducted in the field of individual games, including tennis, to determine the special and necessary requirements for that game through the use of appropriate teaching methods, which are among the most important factors affecting learning the technical performance of the skill and developing the most important motor characteristics associated with it, as well as contributing to the learner reaching the best level of skill performance, especially if it is used effectively and correctly.

The generative learning strategy "is one of the modern learning strategies, it is a method for learning and teaching at the same time, as students participate in activities and exercises very effectively, through a rich and

varied learning environment, so this strategy is based on learning, in order to understand or learn based on meaning, by linking the learner's past experiences with his subsequent experiences, And the formation of connections and relationships between them, or the learner builds through generative processes that he uses in modifying alternative perceptions and special concepts in the light of correct scientific knowledge" .

1-2 Research problem

The research problem is manifested by answering the following two questions:

Is there an effect of a generative learning strategy on learning the skill of serving in tennis? Is the proposed strategy more useful than the traditional method for teaching the skill of serving on tennis?

1-3 Research goal

Identifying the effect of using an educational approach proposed by a generative learning strategy on learning the skill of serving in tennis.

1-4 Research hypotheses

- 1- There are statistically significant differences between the pre and post tests in learning the skill of serving for tennis.
- 2- There are statistically significant differences in the level of performance between the post tests in learning the skill of serving for tennis.

1-5 Research fields

- 1-5-1 the human field: a sample of the distinguished middle school students for boys, for the age groups (16-17) years
- 1-5-2 the spatial field: the outer yard, Al Mutamaizen Prep for Boys
- 1-5-3 Time field: for the period from (17/2/2019) to (21/4/2019)

2- Research methodology and field procedures

2-1 Research Methodology

The researcher used the experimental approach using one group design, as the experimental method "is the only research method that can truly test the hypotheses of cause and effect relationships. This approach also represents the most honest approach to solving many scientific problems in a scientific and theoretical manner as well as its contributions to the progress of scientific research. In the humanities and social sciences, including sports science.

2-2 The research sample

The research sample consisted of (20) students from Al Mutamaizen Prep for Boys from Baghdad Governorate, aged (16-17) years. The sample was chosen by the intentional method and they were divided into two groups, an experimental group and a control group.

2-3 Sample homogeneity

For the purpose of verifying the homogeneity of the sample members in weight, height and age using the coefficient of variation, as shown in the table below:

Table (1)

It shows the homogeneity of the members of the research sample in the variables of height, weight and age

Variables	$\bar{X}$	σ	median	Cv 3±	Sample size
Height / cm	156.6	4.472	157.5	74.2	20
Weight / Kg	55.9	6.838	54.5	78	
Age / year	13.3	1.158	12.9	70.5	

Table (1) shows the values of the coefficient of variation values in the three variables between ± 3 , indicating that the livelihood of the research sample is homogeneous in the variables (weight - age).

For this, the experimental and control groups are equal in the skill performance of the transmission. (T) was used for correlated samples, and it appeared that there is a difference indicating the equivalence of two groups of common groups in Table (2):

Table (2)

The parity of the two experimental groups is shown in the pre-service skill tests and the calculated (T) value

Skill	Experimental Group		Control group		Computed value	T	Statistical significance
	$\bar{X}$	σ	$\bar{X}$	σ			
The serve	2.399	0.374	2.166	0.64	0.72		random

Tabular value (T) = (1.86) at a level of significance (0.05) and degree of freedom(18)

2-4 tools and devices used and means of gathering information

2-4-1 Research tools

- 1- Tennis court (1)
- 2- Tennis rackets (20)
- 3- Tennis balls (50)
- 4- Antenna (2)
- 5- Tennis net (1)
- 6- A tape measure (1)
- 7- Ropes + ribbons.

2-4-2 Devices used

- 1- Personal Computer.
- 2- A medical scale to measure weight

2-4-3 Information gathering methods

- 1- Arabic and foreign sources.
- 2- Skills tests.

2-6 Exploratory experiment

The exploratory experiment (it is a preliminary experimental study that the researcher performs on a small sample before performing it in order to test research methods and tools).

The researcher conducted an exploratory experiment on 15/2/2019 on a small sample of (6) players, where the consistency and objectivity of the tests used in the research were verified, the efficiency of the assisting team, and the devices and tools used in the tests.

2-7 Tests used in the research

2-7-1 Hewitt's serve test

- The purpose of the test: to measure the accuracy of the serve.
- Devices and tools: (tennis court - tennis balls - tennis rackets - tapes - antennas).
- Performance description: The tested player performs the service behind the baseline for (9) successive attempts on the targets set in the opposite half of the court, provided that all the balls pass between the legal net of the tennis court and the rope installed between the two ends of the net from the top so that the distance between the rope and the net is (4) feet. The goals are divided into (6) areas and where the player tries to get the highest score by dropping the ball in zone no. (6) in order to get the highest score.

Figure (1) shows the layout of the tennis court in the serve accuracy test.

2-8 Field research procedures

2-8-1 Pre-tests

Pre-tests are one of the means of evaluation, measurement, diagnosis and orientation in curricula and programs for all levels and age stages, as they play the role of an indicator clearly, i.e. progress and success in achieving the set goal.

The pre-tests were conducted to evaluate the technical performance on 17/2/2019 for the skill of transmission. The tests were conducted at (10) in the morning under the supervision of the researcher and the teacher. The pre-tests were conducted using the Hewitt serve accuracy test.

Educational curriculum:

The educational curriculum for the research sample was implemented on Monday 18/2/2019 and was completed on Thursday 18/4/2019 for the members of the experimental group. For weeks with two educational units per week (Monday and Tuesday), and at a time of (45) for one educational unit, as the generative learning strategy was worked out in the main part of the two educational unit, the time of which is (30) minutes. One exercise (5) minutes between one exercise and the last one minute to rest, and preparing the second exercise when the researcher completes the exploratory experiment and the pre-tests

The researcher intended to prepare a special educational curriculum for the members of the experimental group according to the generative learning strategy, this strategy includes the participation of the learner in the educational process in developing some basic skills in ground tennis and concentrating the researcher's work in the main section of the educational unit, as the researchers in the first educational unit know the rules of the game and basic skills in ground tennis and determine the skill of serving, as the researcher explained the concept of the skill of serving and when to use the skill of serving, what the important foundations are that must be taken into account during the concept of the skill of serving, and after that the researcher wrote the exercises with illustrations for each exercise in a detailed way using educational methods such as the whiteboard, and explain

each exercise and apply it before moving on to explain the second exercise, and so on to the rest of the other exercises, And through the exercises that the researcher explained on the blackboard, the researcher assigned the students an assignment sheet or (work) due to the researcher's lack of interest in the educational aspect. The assignment paper included:

- What the basic skills are.
- Learn the rules of the game.
- What the concept of serving skill is.
- When to use the sending skill.
- What the important principles to consider during the skill of serving are.

2-8-3 Post-tests

After completing the educational curriculum and its vocabulary for the skill of serving, a post-test was conducted for the research sample on (21/4/2019), and the researcher prepared in advance the appropriate conditions in terms of time and place and tools for the post-test and the implementation of the procedures followed in the pre-test and with the help of the same cadres in the pre-test.

2-9 Statistical methods

- 1) The arithmetic mean.
- 2) Standard deviation.
- 3) Coefficient of variance.
- 4) Correlated samples (T) test.

3- Presenting tests results and their analysis and discussion

This chapter deals with presenting, analyzing and discussing the results of the research through collecting data, processing it statistically, and examining the objectives that were mentioned in the research.

3-1 Presenting, analysis and discussion of the results of the serve skill evaluation

Table (3) Shows the results of the pre and post skill tests and the value (T) calculated for the two experimental and control groups in the performance of serving skill

The group	Pretest		Post-test		Computed (T) value	Tabular (T) value	Statistical significance
	$\bar{X}$	σ	$\bar{X}$	σ			
Experimental	2.399		0.37		6.35	2.13	incorporeal
Control	2.166		0.64		2.03		

Under the level of significance (0.05) and the degree of freedom(9)

Table (3) shows the results of evaluating the serve skill for the experimental group, where the results of the arithmetic mean and standard deviation of the pre-test for the first experimental group were (2.39) and (0.374) and for the post test (4.111) and (0.53) for the purpose of knowing the significance of the significant differences in the arithmetic media between the two pre-tests The post-test for the experimental group was used for the (T) test for the corresponding samples, as its calculated value reached (6.35), which is greater than the tabular value (2.13) and at a degree of freedom (9) and below the significance level (0.05), which indicates the presence of significant differences in favor of the post test. The arithmetic and the standard deviation in the pre-test for the control group were (2.16) and (0.64), and for the post test (2.06) and (0.92). As for the value of (T) calculated to know the significance of the differences between the pretest and the post test, it was (2.03) which is smaller than the table value (2.13).) With a degree of freedom (9) and below the level of significance (0.05), which indicates that there are no significant differences

Table (4)It shows the results of the post skill tests and the value (T) calculated between the two groups in the performance of the skill of serving

The group	Post-test		Computed (T) value	Tabular (T) value	Statistical significance
	$\bar{X}$	σ			
Experimental	4.111	0.53	2.81	2.81	incorporeal
Control	2.06	0.92			

Under the level of significance (0.05) and the degree of freedom(18)

The value of the (T) calculated test was (2.81), which is greater than the tabular value (1.86), with a degree of freedom (18) and below the level of (0.05), which indicates the presence of significant differences in favor of the post test of the experimental group, which was considered the best effect of learning, since its arithmetic mean is greater When discussing the results of the research that were presented in Table (3) for the pre and post-

tests of the two groups, it appeared that there is a significant difference in learning the skill of sending and in favor of the experimental group.

The researcher attributes this development to the procedures that followed modern training by the teacher who can communicate the skill in a simple series, especially since the serve is a base for any tennis player, as well as educational recreational games that affect the learning and improve the performance of the skill in its correct manner and instill confidence in the students themselves and not just correct their mistakes in order to It does not affect his psychological state.

In addition, the level of the tests indicates the effectiveness of this strategy, as it includes research, inquiry, and discussion of the steps in detailing the skill to be learned by the learners, thus achieving it, and with the teacher on the other hand, through the learning activity in order to reach the optimum and then final exten.) Likewise, the learners interact with each other to support their learning and raise their level of education, and that the generative learning strategy includes helping learners with each other in an effective system, which helps in achieving the learning goals,

This is confirmed by (Al-Rubaie and Amin: 2010), "Whatever the method used to learn a skill, training is not sufficient, because the player doesn't learn skill and knowledge, unless through interaction between the learners, which helps to increase learning."

4- Conclusions and recommendations

4-1 Conclusions

Through the findings of the researcher and the use of statistical means, he reached the following:

- 1- The educational program through the educational units has achieved its objectives for which it was set by learning the skill of sending in tennis.
- 2- The experimental group in the post-tests achieved a greater development than the control group.

4-2 Recommendations

The researcher recommends the following:

Emphasis on the use of a generative learning strategy and in other sporting events.

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